

SOCIAL MEDIA - CHARACTERS

[Hermanni, A.-J. (2015) / Revision 2022]

	Persona A	Persona B	Persona C	Persona D
	Fast Seller	Business Executive	Event Hopper	Partner Surfer
Personas (Description)	<p>Behavior: Transaction-oriented communication with a focus on short-term business deals; assertive demeanor; focus on monetary objectives.</p> <p>Self-interest and calculating benefits are strongly pronounced. They want simple, immediate business deals and quick profits.</p> <p>In many cases, the fast salesperson changes sectors repeatedly or runs several vendor's tray businesses at the same time.</p> <p>Everyday life is characterized by fear of the future and few opportunities for advancement.</p>	<p>Behavior: Long-term network management; professional and strategic relationship management; focus on mutual business added value.</p> <p>Business contacts are characterized by efficiency orientation, a sense of status and a pronounced claim to leadership. They have an intellectual character, are professionally and socially established and open to innovative solutions.</p> <p>Their responsible actions prevent them from instrumentalizing social contacts for short-term transactions. Instead, they pursue a sustainable networking strategy.</p>	<p>Behavior: Participation in events primarily for social or entertainment purposes; no specific business objective; informal communication.</p> <p>The event hopper is not primarily defined by professional status or academic background. Rather, it is a mixed group - from ordinary employees to civil servants and pensioners.</p> <p>Event hoppers do not use the platform for explicitly professional purposes, but to maintain private contacts, for networking out of personal interest or to participate in events without any strategic business connection.</p>	<p>Behavior: Privately motivated contact; use of the platform to initiate personal relationships; focus on interpersonal exchange.</p> <p>Partner surfers are generally singles who are specifically looking for partnerships or friendships without resorting to traditional dating platforms.</p> <p>This user group is characterized by the indirect search for interpersonal relationships via business portals. They often prefer this approach as it allows them to make contacts without being immediately categorized as single or looking for someone.</p>
Demographic classification	<p>Fast salespeople" are often people who are not necessarily academically trained or hold traditional management positions.</p> <p>Average income: € 30,000 - 50,000 gross/year, sometimes fluctuating strongly, commission-based.</p>	<p>Business contacts have predominantly medium to higher educational qualifications and are often employed in managerial or qualified positions.</p> <p>As a rule, they have a medium to high income: approx. 50,000 - 80,000 € gross/year.</p>	<p>Predominantly intermediate educational qualifications (e.g. secondary school leaving certificate, advanced technical college entrance qualification) and basic professional qualifications.</p> <p>Rather stable income (employees, civil servants, pensioners), rarely high: approx. 30,000 - 45,000 € gross/year.</p>	<p>The majority of partner surfers have an intermediate level of education or professional qualifications. There is no discernible concentration of academically highly qualified users within this group.</p> <p>The income level is between € 35,000 and € 50,000 gross per year.</p>